

Determination of Dissociation Constants pK_a of Hydroxyquinoline Derivatives

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Dissociation constants (pK_a) of hydroxyquinoline derivatives are determined potentiometrically at two different ionic strengths, pyridine-water mixed solvent media and at 20, 30 and 40°. Henderson-Hasselbalch equation adopting Alberts and Serjeant's method was used for calculating these constants.

ORGANIC compounds with quinoline moiety are of much interest to research workers in the field of synthetic, analytical, medicinal chemistry^{1,2}. Determination of protolytic equilibria is closely associated with the development of electrochemistry³. It reveals the proportion of various ionic species into which the given compound dissociates at a particular pH. This has practical applications mainly in the field of medicine and biochemistry. The early phase of investigations revolved around ionisation in aqueous solutions^{4,5}. Synthetic organic and analytical chemists focussed their attention on ionisation studies using non-aqueous or mixed polar solvents, like pyridine-water system⁶.

Quinoline and its derivatives are widely used in formulations. Hence, hydroxyquinoline derivatives were selected for the present investigation.

Experimental

Compounds synthesised for the present study were 4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester (4HQC) (1), 6-nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester (6NHQC) (2), 7-nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester (7NHQC) (3), 8-nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester (8NHQC) (4) and 8-hydroxyquinoline (8HQ) (5). Compounds 1-4 are possible intermediates of antimalarial agents. The synthesis⁷⁻¹⁰ was divided into three stages, viz. (i) synthesis of ethyl ethoxymethylene malonate, (ii) synthesis of ethyl anilinomethylene malonate/nuclear substituted anilinomethylene malonate and (iii) synthesis of 6,7- or 8-nitro-substituted or unsubstituted 4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester. The products were purified, analysed (Table 1). Double-distilled water, redistilled over alkaline $KMnO_4$ was used ($pH \sim 6.8$). Solvent pyridine was refluxed over KOH and redistilled¹¹. Carbonate free KOH stock solution was prepared. After appropriate dilutions and standardisations it was used for titrations. KCl (AnalaR) solution (1 N) was prepared after standardising against $AgNO_3$.

TABLE 1—4-HYDROXYQUINOLINE-3-CARBOXYLIC ESTERS

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p (°C): Found/ (Reported)	Formula
1.	4-Hydroxyquinoline 3-carboxylic ester	270-71 (270-71)	$C_{10}H_{11}O_3N$
2.	4-Hydroxy-6-nitro- quinoline-3-carboxylic ester	>300 (>300)	$C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2$
3.	4-Hydroxy-7-nitro- quinoline-3-carboxylic ester	>300 (>300)	$C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2$
4.	4-Hydroxy-8-nitro- quinoline-3-carboxylic ester	252 (252)	$C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2$

A Toshniwal CL-46 digital pH meter was used, having thermocompensator 0-100° and accuracy range of $pH \pm 0.01$ and ± 1 mV. A Toshniwal glass-calomel electrode assembly reading between 0-14 pH and 0-130° was used. The electrodes were prepared in HCl or water as the case may be, cleaned before and after the experiments. The pH meter assembly was standardised against two standard buffers at 4.000 5 and 9.139 at 25°. Specially jacketed titration assembly with magnetic stirrer was used.

The acid dissociation constant of 4-hydroxyquinolines is attributed to the dissociation of phenolic hydroxyl group attached to the parent nucleus. In aqueous medium, the reaction may be represented as

where, $Q(OH)$ represents the phenolic OH, H_2O the water molecule, QO^- the quinolate ion and H_3O^+ the hydronium ion, or, in general,

where, ns represents the solvent molecule, and $H^+(Sn)$ the protonated solvent molecule. The dissociation constants have been calculated using Henderson-Hasselbalch equation adopting Alberts and Serjeant's method^{12,13}. The hydroxyl ion

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correction was not applied in cases $pH > 11$, especially in the case of 8-hydroxyquinoline and 6-nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester.

Dissociation constants are mainly influenced by¹⁴⁻¹⁷ (i) nature of the solvent media, *i.e.* dielectric constant and basicity or acidity, (ii) ionic strength, (iii) temperature and (iv) nature and position of the substituents in the parent nucleus.

Dependence of dissociation constants on the nature of the solvent media :

The present investigation was carried out using varying composition of pyridine-water mixture. The values of dissociation constant obtained at pyridine-water (50 : 50, 60 : 40 and 70 : 30, v/v) compositions are presented in Table 2. The choice of the mixed solvent, *i.e.* the pyridine-water mixture was due to the insolubility of the hydroxyquinolines in aqueous media and in other common organic solvents.

Pyridine-water Solvent (v/v)	pK_a				
	8HQ	4HQO	6NHQO	7NHQO	8NHQO
$\mu = 0.010$ 1 M, Temp. = 20°					
50 : 50	11.26	10.64	11.40	9.89	9.80
60 : 40	11.71	10.88	11.98	9.94	9.84
70 : 30	12.12	11.07	12.69	9.94	9.87
$\mu = 0.001$ 4 M, Temp. = 20°					
50 : 50	11.81	10.91	10.62	9.95	9.41
60 : 40	11.85	11.07	12.24	10.21	9.44
70 : 30	12.48	11.44	13.08	10.06	9.45
$\mu = 0.010$ 1 M, Temp. = 30°					
50 : 50	11.07	10.87	11.00	9.78	9.15
60 : 40	11.47	10.62	11.48	9.82	9.22
70 : 30	12.15	10.80	12.38	9.84	9.23
$\mu = 0.001$ 4 M, Temp. = 30°					
50 : 50	11.22	10.68	11.25	9.84	9.23
60 : 40	11.69	10.77	11.71	9.80	9.30
70 : 30	12.30	11.07	12.79	10.03	9.32
$\mu = 0.010$ 1 M, Temp. = 40°					
50 : 50	10.93	10.21	10.74	9.70	9.07
60 : 40	11.29	10.42	11.02	9.68	9.10
70 : 30	11.81	10.68	11.74	9.77	9.13
$\mu = 0.001$ 4 M, Temp. = 40°					
50 : 50	11.06	10.36	10.99	9.74	9.11
60 : 40	11.49	10.72	11.36	9.76	9.20
70 : 30	12.13	10.96	12.16	9.95	9.19

The results indicate that as percentage of pyridine increases, the dissociation constants decreases, implying lesser acidity. Mainly two parameters, *viz.* dielectric constant (ϵ) and basicity or acidity of the solvent are responsible for this behaviour of hydroxyquinolines in the given media, *i.e.* pyridine-water mixture.

Dielectric constant : The dielectric constant of a solvent measures its capacity to separate oppositely charged particles. In a solvent with high dielectric constant such as water ($\epsilon = 78.5$ at temperature 25°),

a minimum work is required to separate a positively charged ion from one with negative charge, and for a solvent with low dielectric constant such as acetic acid ($\epsilon = 6.2$ at 25°), a greater amount of energy is required to accomplish this process. This implies that as the dielectric constant of the solvent increases, the degree of dissociation of a solute increases giving a high dissociation constant (K_a). Consequently, pK_a decreases showing high acidity. The dielectric constant of the solvent system were obtained by graphical method (Table 3).

Pyridine-Water (v/v)	Dielectric constant at 25°
Water	78.5
50 : 50	45.5
60 : 40	38.5
70 : 30	32.0
Pyridine	12.0

Basicity or acidity of the solvent : Pyridine is mainly an aprotic basic solvent⁶. The aprotic character represents the total non-availability of any proton for sharing with other atoms or molecules, which is due to its stable aromatic character and high resonance energy of the heterocycle. The presence of the hetero atom nitrogen fused into the conjugate ring system makes pyridine very important as a basic solvent. The acidity of the solute is enhanced due to the affinity of nitrogen in the heterocyclic ring, for hydrogen ion due to the lone-pair electrons. Consequently, with the increase in pyridine percentage the acidity or K_a values should increase or pK_a should decrease. But exactly opposite results have been obtained in the titrations as is evident from the Tables. This discrepancy may be explained as follows. (i) With the increase in pyridine percentage, though the basicity of the solvent increases, its dielectric constant (ϵ) decreases. (ii) The effect of dielectric constant and that of basicity of the solvent, on dissociation are opposite and hence, there should be a dynamic equilibrium. (iii) The effect of dielectric constant being prominent masks the effect of basicity and hence the contradiction. (iv) Water molecules are universally known to solvate hydrogen ions. It is possible that, the affinity of heterocyclic nitrogen towards hydrogen ions may be less than the energy required to break the solvent sheath of hydrogen ions formed by water molecules.

Determination of aqueous dissociation constants of the compound : The aqueous dissociation constants of the compounds under study have been computed graphically¹⁸. Dissociation constant of the compounds at various percentage pyridine was plotted against respective solvent percentage, and extrapolated to zero percent pyridine (Table 4).

This type of a study was found necessary mainly for comparative purposes with that of the reported values. The acid dissociation constant of

TABLE 4

Temp. °C	pK _a at ionic strength	
	μ = 0.010 1 M	μ = 0.001 4 M
8-Hydroxyquinoline		
20	9.15	8.60
30	8.80	8.45
40	8.70	8.30
4-Hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester		
20	9.75	9.5
30	9.30	9.1
40	9.15	8.8
6-Nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester		
20	8.35	8.00
30	8.10	7.65
40	7.90	7.50
7-Nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester		
20	9.50	9.15
30	9.40	9.10
40	9.35	9.20
8-Nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester		
20	9.1	8.95
30	8.9	8.65
40	8.8	8.50

8-hydroxyquinoline at ionic strength 0.5 and at temperature 25° was reported to be 9.81. In the present investigation at 20°, it was found to be 8.82 at 0.001 4 ionic strength. A decrease in pK_a value can be noted due to the decreased ionic strength. This study was more necessitated for confirming the reliability of the technique and methods used, as the values of dissociation constants available in pyridine-water mixture are considerably less.

Dependence of dissociation constants on the ionic strength :

In the present work, dissociation constant determination was done at two ionic strengths, μ = 0.010 1 and 0.001 4 M, using the electrolyte KCl. For a comparative study, the values of such determinations including values in pure aqueous medium are given in Table 5. A close observation of the values reveals that in pyridine-water mixture, the dissociation constant increases as ionic strength increases. To take 8-hydroxyquinoline as an example, at 20° in 50% pyridine and at ionic strength 0.010 1 M, pK_a is 11.26, whereas at ionic strength 0.010 M, pK_a is 11.31, showing a decrease in dissociation constant K_a.

In aqueous media, the ionic strength (μ) is related to the activity coefficient^{19,20} as

$$-\log f_1 = AZ_1^2 \mu^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where, f₁ is activity coefficient, A is a constant, and Z₁ is ionic charge. Activity and activity coefficients are related by the equation

$$a_1 Z_1 = C_1 f_1 \quad (2)$$

where, C₁ is concentration, and a₁ is activity. From equations (1) and (2) it is clear that an increase in

TABLE 5

Pyridine - Water (v/v)	pK _a values at μ = 0.010 1 M			pK _a values at μ = 0.001 4 M		
	20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°
8-Hydroxyquinoline						
Water	9.15	8.8	8.7	8.6	8.45	8.3
50 : 50	11.26	11.07	10.98	11.81	11.22	11.06
60 : 40	11.71	11.47	11.29	11.65	11.69	11.49
70 : 30	12.12	12.15	11.81	12.48	12.30	12.13
4-Hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester						
Water	9.15	9.30	9.15	9.50	9.10	8.80
50 : 50	10.64	10.37	10.209	10.91	10.68	10.36
60 : 40	10.83	10.62	10.42	11.07	10.77	10.72
70 : 30	11.07	10.80	10.68	11.44	11.07	10.96
6-Nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester						
Water	8.35	8.10	7.90	8.00	7.65	7.5
50 : 50	11.40	11.00	10.74	11.62	11.25	10.99
60 : 40	11.93	11.48	11.02	12.24	11.71	11.36
70 : 30	12.69	12.33	11.74	13.08	12.79	12.16
7-Nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester						
Water	9.50	9.40	9.35	9.15	4.10	9.20
50 : 50	9.89	9.78	9.70	9.95	9.84	9.74
60 : 40	9.94	9.82	9.68	10.21	9.80	9.76
70 : 30	9.94	9.84	9.77	10.06	10.03	9.95
8-Nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester						
Water	9.10	8.90	8.80	8.95	8.65	8.50
50 : 50	9.30	9.15	9.07	9.41	9.23	9.11
60 : 40	9.34	9.22	9.10	9.44	9.30	9.20
70 : 30	9.37	9.23	9.13	9.45	9.32	9.19

ionic strength decreases the activity coefficient and consequently the activity. Activity and dissociation constant are related directly and hence a decrease in activity will decrease the dissociation constant K_a, making the solute less acidic. The same trend was observed in cases where pK_a values were determined in pure aqueous media. pK_a of 8-hydroxyquinoline in water at 20° and at ionic strength 0.001 4 is 8.6, and at ionic strength 0.010 1 M it is 9.15 showing a decrease in dissociation constant (K_a) value and consequently the acidity.

Conclusion :

Hydroxyquinoline derivatives, one of the ingredients used in formulations, could be effective only under certain pH value. Release of organic moiety in gastrointestinal tract could only be achieved with the knowledge of its dissociation constants. The present work adds to such knowledge which in turn could help the biochemists and medical fraternity to incorporate hydroxyquinoline derivatives in particular formulations, such as antimalarials and allied preparations.

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